

Equilibrium and synthetic studies of homo- and heterobinuclear complexes of DTPA with Zn^{II} and some transition and alkaline earth metal ions

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Manuscript received 23 July 2007, accepted 13 September 2007

Abstract : The metal-ligand stability constants for the homo- and heterobinuclear complexes of the type ZnLM (L = diethylene triamine pentaacetic acid; M = Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}) have been determined in aqueous medium using Irving-Rossotti potentiometric titration technique at constant ionic strength $I = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaNO₃) in the biologically relevant conditions. The stability constants have been evaluated using SCOGS computer program. Synthetic studies have been done by isolation and characterization of the above complexes. Further informations about the structure of these complexes have been obtained from the IR spectra.

Keywords : Equilibrium, binuclear, DTPA, zinc(II).

In recent years, a number of acyclic polyamino carboxylic acids like EDTA and DTPA have been developed for complexation of metal ions *in vivo* applications¹ and as antidotes² in heavy metal detoxification. There have been a few studies in recent years to investigate the coordination chemistry of these metals in both aqueous and non-aqueous media³. Apart from the fact that these elements were involved with some of the earliest forms of life due to their important role in DNA and protein synthesis⁴, they also play other roles in life processes⁵.

The study of coordination of these metals with simple, commonly available polyaminocarboxylic acids would be of interest as it would model the coordination behaviour of natural aminoacids to biologically relevant metal ions⁶. In the present study we report the synthetic and structural

investigations on the homo- and heterobinuclear complexes of DTPA with Zn^{II} involving Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II} and Ba^{II} respectively at $37 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The solution studies deals with the potentiometric studies of the formation of homo- and heterobinuclear complexes of DTPA with Zn^{II} involving Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Cd^{II} respectively at $37 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique⁷. The hydrolysis of metal ions has been taken into account wherever it interfered with the stability constant measurements. The mixed-metal complexes have been isolated in the solid-state and studied by elemental analysis, metal analysis and infrared spectroscopy.

Materials and methods :

A stock solution (0.01 M) of diethylenetriamine-

Table 1. Physical properties and analytical data of complexes

Formula	Colour	Decomposition temp. ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Analysis (experimental)					Analysis (theoretical)				
			C	H	N	Zn	IInd metal	C	H	N	Zn	IInd metal
Zn ^{II} -DTPA	Light yellow	188	24.48	3.36	7.95	29.72	4.10	25.87	2.93	6.43	30.82	3.68
Zn ^{II} -DTPA- Mg ^{II} .2H ₂ O	Light yellow	192	25.19	3.08	6.92	30.11	5.22	25.27	2.86	6.31	30.16	6.02
Zn ^{II} -DTPA- Ca ^{II} .2H ₂ O	Light yellow	194	22.03	2.58	4.66	27.47	13.74	23.58	2.27	5.51	28.08	12.28
Zn ^{II} -DTPA- Sr ^{II} .2H ₂ O	Light yellow	191	22.87	2.59	4.67	26.75	17.92	22.05	2.48	5.49	26.32	17.98

pentaacetic acid (DTPA) was prepared by dissolving into two equivalents of NaOH. Solutions of Zn^{II}, Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Cd^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} metal ions were prepared and standardised by EDTA titrations. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide (E. Merck) and nitric acid (A.R.) were prepared in doubly distilled water and standardised as usual. A digital pH-meter (century model-CP 901-S) with a glass electrode was used for pH measurements. The following sets of solutions were prepared keeping the total volume 50.0 ml in each case and the molar ratio of primary metal, secondary metal and the ligand are formed to the homo- and heterobinuclear (1 : 1 : 1) complexes :

- Set I : 5 ml HNO₃ (0.02 M) + 5 ml NaNO₃ (1 M) + 40 ml H₂O
- Set II : 5 ml HNO₃ (0.02 M) + 5 ml NaNO₃ (1 M) + 5 ml DTPA (0.01 M) + 35 ml H₂O
- Set III : 5 ml HNO₃ (0.02 M) + 5 ml NaNO₃ (1 M) + 5 ml DTPA (0.01 M) + 5 ml Zn^{II} (0.01 M) + 30 ml H₂O
- Set IV : 5 ml HNO₃ (0.02 M) + 5 ml NaNO₃ (1 M) + 5 ml DTPA (0.01 M) + 10 ml Zn^{II} (0.01 M) + 25 ml H₂O
- Set V : 5 ml HNO₃ (0.02 M) + 5 ml NaNO₃ (1 M) + 5 ml DTPA (0.01 M) + 5 ml Zn^{II} (0.01 M) + 5 ml M₂ (0.01 M) + 25 ml H₂O

where, M₂ = Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}. All the solutions were thermostated at 37 ± 1 °C and titrated against 0.1 M NaOH. The values of \bar{n}_H , \bar{n} and pL have been calculated from the titration curves by Irving-Rossotti method. Preliminary estimates of binary and

ternary constants obtained by least square method⁷ were used as input data for running the SCOGS computer program⁸. The other experimental details were the same as described elsewhere⁹.

Table 3. Stability constant values for the metal ligand (2 : 1) complexes : homobimetallic system

Reaction [metal : ligand (2 : 1)]			log β
Zn ²⁺	+	DTPA ⁵⁻ ⇌ [Zn-DTPA-Zn] ⁻	22.79
Pb ²⁺	+	DTPA ⁵⁻ ⇌ [Pb-DTPA-Pb] ⁻	22.06
Be ²⁺	+	DTPA ⁵⁻ ⇌ [Be-DTPA-Be] ⁻	9.64
Mg ²⁺	+	DTPA ⁵⁻ ⇌ [Mg-DTPA-Mg] ⁻	10.36
Sr ²⁺	+	DTPA ⁵⁻ ⇌ [Sr-DTPA-Sr] ⁻	10.68
Ba ²⁺	+	DTPA ⁵⁻ ⇌ [Ba-DTPA-Ba] ⁻	9.75

Preparation of complexes : The chelates were prepared by refluxing the appropriate amount of ligand DTPA and the metal salts in requisite amount by keeping the molar ratio as 1 : 1 : 1. The precipitated complex was digested on water bath, filtered, washed and dried. Elemental analysis was done at CDRI, Lucknow. The analysis of metal ions in the complexes were carried out by standard methods¹⁰. The results of the analysis as well as physical properties are listed in Table 1. FTIR spectra of the ligand H₃Zn^{II}-DTPA and its heterobinuclear chelates were recorded in Nujol mulls/KBr disc/CsI/CHCl₃ with the help of Shimadzu spectrophotometer, model 820 IPC. Table 2 contains the important characteristic IR absorption frequencies of the ligand and its heterobinuclear complexes.

Table 4. Stability constant values for the Zn^{II}-L-M^{II} type complexes of DTPA at 37 ± 1° and μ = 0.1 mol dm⁻³ (NaNO₃)

Reaction			log β ₁₁₁₀₀
Zn ²⁺ + DTPA ⁵⁻ + Co ²⁺	⇌	[Zn-DTPA-Co] ⁻	21.95
Zn ²⁺ + DTPA ⁵⁻ + Ni ²⁺	⇌	[Zn-DTPA-Ni] ⁻	23.82
Zn ²⁺ + DTPA ⁵⁻ + Cu ²⁺	⇌	[Zn-DTPA-Cu] ⁻	24.98
Zn ²⁺ + DTPA ⁵⁻ + Cd ²⁺	⇌	[Zn-DTPA-Cd] ⁻	20.53
Zn ²⁺ + DTPA ⁵⁻ + Be ²⁺	⇌	[Zn-DTPA-Be] ⁻	19.38
Zn ²⁺ + DTPA ⁵⁻ + Mg ²⁺	⇌	[Zn-DTPA-Mg] ⁻	19.83

Table 2. Infrared absorption table of DTPA and Zn^{II}-DTPA-alkaline earth metal complexes

Complexes	H ₂ O or ROH	-CH	-OH	-COOH	-COOM	-COOH
Ligand DTPA	3495.2	3024.0	2773.4	1732.0	-	1218.9
Zn ^{II} -DTPA	3417.2	3020.0	2770.4	1690.0	1621.0	1220.9
Zn ^{II} -DTPA-Mg ^{II} .2H ₂ O	3380.2	2980.7	2775.0	-	1578.5	1218.7
Zn ^{II} -DTPA-Ca ^{II} .2H ₂ O	3430.9	2964.4	2774.2	-	1616.2	1257.5
Zn ^{II} -DTPA-Sr ^{II} .2H ₂ O	3402.2	2964.5	2625.5	-	1585.5	1260.5
Zn ^{II} -DTPA-Ba ^{II} .2H ₂ O	3425.5	2859.5	2681.5	-	1592.5	1258.5

Results and discussion

Diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid acts as an octadentate ligand. In the binary complex Zn^{II}-DTPA, Zn^{II} is expected to bound two amino-nitrogen and two carboxylato groups. However, it has still three vacant coordination sites available for interaction with another metal ion and thus making the formation of mixed-metal complex possible with DTPA.

Homobimetallic complexes (2 : 1) : Table 3 represents the refined values of binary complex species of M^{II}-DTPA systems taken under study. Besides the complex M^{II}-DTPA-M^{II}, H₃L, H₂L species of the ligand and free metal ions are also identifiable. Both H₃L and M^{II} species are present in the decreasing order of their concentrations indicating their involvement in homobinuclear complexation as per equilibrium :

The metal-ligand formation constants of metal to ligand complexes in 2 : 1 ratio have been found to follow the order : Be₂L < Ba₂L < Mg₂L < Sr₂L < Zn₂L. It is evident from the distribution curves that Zn^{II} is complexed with DTPA in 2 : 1 metal to ligand ratio. The homobimetallic complexation starts from pH ≈ 3 and with the increase in pH₂ there is an increase in its concentration attaining a maximum value at pH ≈ 6.0. However, when alkaline earth metals are complexed with DTPA forming homobimetallic complexes, the complexation starts beyond pH ≈ 6.5. Thus, it may be concluded that the homobimetallic complexes with transition metals are formed at low pH region while with alkaline earth metal ions are formed at high pH region.

Heterobimetallic complexes (1 : 1 : 1) : The formation of ternary complex is deduced from the fact that the curve corresponding to mixed-metal species diverges from the titration curves corresponding to primary metal Zn^{II}, right from the beginning of the titration. Speciation curves show the existence of protonated ligand species, free metal ions, binary complex species along with the ternary complex species. The formation of ternary complex may be defined by the equation :

where, M₁ = Zn^{II} and M₂ = the secondary metal ions under study and L = DTPA. The overall stability constants (log β) of these heterobinuclear complexes have been presented in Table 4. The stability constants of M₁-L-M₂ systems fall in the following order :

All the metal complexes do not show absorption frequencies corresponding to -COOH group (at 1700 cm⁻¹)

indicating that the -COOH proton is displaced by metal ions. The peaks observed for Zn^{II}-DTPA are at (i) 3417.2 cm⁻¹, (ii) 3020.2 cm⁻¹, (iii) 2770.4 cm⁻¹, (iv) 1690.0 cm⁻¹, (v) 1621.0 cm⁻¹ and (vi) 1220.9 cm⁻¹, which represent (i) H₂O or ROH vibration, (ii) -CH vibration, (iii) -OH (carboxyl group) vibration.

The complexes with Zn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Be^{II} and other alkaline earth metal ions are four coordinated and may possibly have a tetrahedral geometry while Cd^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes are six-coordinated and have an octahedral geometry. The proposed structures of these heterobinuclear complexes seem to be convincing, because stereochemistry of the compound like Na₂Mg^{II}-EDTA.H₂O, Ba^{II}-Cu^{II}-EDTA.5H₂O have already been established¹¹.

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